

Physical-Layer Security in OFDM-Based PNC-Enabled IoT: Analysis and Detection of Symbol-Level Jamming Attacks

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Abstract—This paper investigates Symbol-Level Jamming (SLJ) detection in Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM)-based Two-Way Relay Channel (TWRC) systems using synchronous Physical-layer Network Coding (PNC). The system includes a relay node exposed to SLJ, characterized by Jamming-to-Signal Ratio (JSR) and duty cycle parameters. Three pilot-assisted detection methods are evaluated: energy-based, Error Vector Magnitude (EVM)-based, and one-class Support Vector Machine (SVM)-based. Simulation results demonstrate that while the energy-based detection performs adequately under strong jamming, its sensitivity diminishes at lower jamming power levels. In a mobile network with low JSR levels (e.g., JSR=-5 dB), the EVM-based detector improves robustness by leveraging constellation distortion metrics, achieving accuracy and precision of 0.97 and 0.87, respectively. On the other hand, the SVM-based method, trained on EVM features extracted from clean symbols, achieves the highest detection performance, with accuracy and precision of 0.99 and 0.97, respectively. Metric selection depends on the application—precision is critical for jammer localization, while accuracy is for network rerouting. The proposed approach enhances SLJ resilience in OFDM-PNC systems.

Keywords—error vector magnitude (EVM), Jamming Detection, Physical-layer Network Coding, support vector machine (SVM), Synchronous PNC.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of the Internet of Things (IoT) across industrial, urban, and critical infrastructure domains has introduced substantial challenges in ensuring scalable and

robust physical-layer security. The integration of IoT with 5G and emerging 6G networks enables massive connectivity, ultra-low latency, and ubiquitous access, while simultaneously exposing these systems to increasingly sophisticated security threats. Wireless channels are inherently vulnerable to malicious exploits, including eavesdropping, spoofing, and jamming attacks, which challenge the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of communications. [1], [2], [3], [4].

Unlike unintentional interference caused by environmental factors, jamming constitutes deliberate interference aimed at degrading or denying service availability [1], [3]. Cellular networks remain particularly susceptible, as attackers may target control and synchronization channels such as the Synchronization Signal Block (SSB) and Physical Broadcast Channel (PBCH). Even low-power narrowband jammers have demonstrated the ability to significantly disrupt network access and synchronization in 5G New Radio (NR) systems [1], [2]. These risks are amplified in IoT ecosystems, where devices operate under severe energy, computational, and protocol constraints. Lightweight IoT protocols such as NB-IoT, Zigbee, and LoRa often lack advanced physical-layer defenses, rendering them vulnerable even to low-energy uplink control channel jamming [5].

To address coverage and capacity limitations, relay-based communications have been widely adopted across wireless standards, including IEEE 802.11s, IEEE 802.16j, LTE-A, and 5G NR. The Two-Way Relay Channel (TWRC), utilizing Physical-layer Network Coding (PNC), enables bidirectional

data exchange within two time slots, improving spectral efficiency. PNC schemes can be generally categorized as asynchronous or synchronous. In asynchronous PNC, transmissions from multiple users may arrive at the relay with time misalignments, which are compensated using receiver-side processing to handle symbol misalignments and carrier offsets. In contrast, synchronous PNC requires accurate coordination so that user signals arrive at the relay with precise time and phase alignment. While synchronous PNC offers improved decoding performance under controlled conditions, it is more vulnerable to precise jamming attacks that target symbol-level superpositions [6]. In this work, a synchronous Decode-and-Forward (DF)-PNC model is adopted due to its structured signaling properties and its susceptibility to sophisticated symbol-level jamming scenarios.

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) is the core transmission technique in modern wireless systems, including Wi-Fi, 4G LTE, and 5G NR, due to its resilience to multipath fading and high spectral efficiency. However, OFDM's multicarrier structure introduces vulnerability to various jamming strategies. These include single-tone, sub-band, and barrage jamming, as well as more advanced jamming approaches such as reactive, random, protocol-aware, and delusive jammers. Among these, symbol-level jamming (SLJ) represents one of the most sophisticated threats. By injecting interference precisely at OFDM symbol boundaries, SLJ enables attackers to cause severe degradation while remaining energy-efficient and difficult to detect [7].

To counter such evolving threats, jamming detection has become a critical first step in protecting communication systems from intentional interference. Effective anti-jamming countermeasures such as interference alignment, frequency hopping, and beamforming depend fundamentally on the ability to detect the presence of jamming, identify its structure, and extract key signal statistics [8]. Detection methods have advanced from simple threshold-based techniques, based on performance metrics like signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), bit error rate (BER) [8], error vector magnitude (EVM) [9], and packet delivery ratio, to more advanced machine learning (ML)-based classifiers that leverage spectral features and in-phase/quadrature (IQ) samples [2], [5], [10], [11]. However, despite these advancements, many existing solutions perform poorly under low Jamming-to-Signal Ratio (JSR) conditions. This challenge remains insufficiently addressed and forms the core motivation for this study.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as below:

- To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work to evaluate SLJ in multicarrier OFDM systems employing synchronous PNC over a Two-Way Relay Channel.
- We conduct a comprehensive evaluation of pilot-assisted SLJ detection methods, including energy-based, EVM-based, and one-class support vector machine (SVM)-based approaches, across varying JSR levels and duty cycle parameters. These findings support the development of a generalizable and

application-aware detection framework for secure OFDM-PNC communications under SLJ conditions.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the state-of-the-art. Section III presents the system model, while the simulation setup and the evaluation results are presented in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Jamming attacks in wireless networks have been extensively studied, particularly as adaptive attackers increasingly exploit protocol-specific vulnerabilities. In synchronous PNC-enabled TWRC systems, SLJ poses a particularly severe threat. Since PNC depends on precise symbol-level superposition at the relay, even minor disruptions can propagate decoding errors and cause complete communication failures.

Jamming attacks can be categorized along several dimensions based on their operational characteristics. From a frequency-domain perspective, spot jamming concentrates energy narrowly on specific subcarriers, achieving high power efficiency but allowing victims to evade through frequency hopping or subcarrier reassignment. In contrast, barrage jamming spreads interference across the entire available frequency spectrum, overwhelming the system but requiring higher power consumption. Other frequency-based types include sweep jamming, which cyclically scans frequency bands according to a predefined pattern, and random jamming, which selects frequencies in a stochastic manner to complicate avoidance strategies.

Temporal behavior also differentiates jammers. Constant jammers transmit continuously, causing persistent performance degradation. Reactive jammers increase stealth by monitoring the channel and emitting interference only upon detecting legitimate transmissions. Meanwhile, random jammers alternate between active and idle states to conserve energy and evade detection. Furthermore, protocol awareness further distinguishes jammers. Protocol-aware and deceptive jammers exploit knowledge of MAC-layer and PHY-layer signaling to mimic or disrupt specific control messages such as RTS/CTS handshakes, beacon frames, or 5G NR's synchronization and broadcast signals (e.g., SSB, PBCH). This undermines both synchronization and access procedures, significantly impacting network functionality. At a higher level of sophistication, smart jammers employ sensing, learning, or mimicry techniques to maximize disruption while remaining covert. These advanced adversaries may adapt to channel conditions, transmission schedules, or network defenses, posing significant challenges to conventional countermeasures [3]. In 5G NR systems, attacks targeting control channels, especially synchronization and broadcast signals, severely impact network accessibility [1], [2]. These threats are particularly devastating in IoT scenarios, where resource-constrained devices have limited defense capabilities.

To address these threats, various mitigation mechanisms have been proposed. Early detection approaches include rule-based methods that apply thresholds to parameters such as SNR, BER [8], EVM [9], or packet delivery ratio, raising

alarms when values fall below predefined limits. While these approaches are computationally simple, they lack adaptability in dynamic channel conditions. Statistical anomaly detection methods improve robustness by monitoring deviations in system performance over time and leveraging historical signal behavior to infer probabilistic anomalies. While effective under stationary conditions, their performance often degrades in non-stationary environments. Fuzzy logic-based systems offer enhanced robustness to uncertainty and complex input relationships but depend heavily on expert knowledge for rule formulation [10].

With the growing sophistication of jammers, Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) approaches have gained prominence. Supervised models such as SVM, k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), decision trees, and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been applied to spectrograms and extracted features for accurate classification. CNN-based models, in particular, demonstrate superior detection accuracy and low latency in scenarios involving SSB distortions [3], [11]. To enable real-time operation in TWRC systems at high symbol rates, online learning algorithms such as Hoeffding trees have been investigated, allowing incremental learning from streaming data without retraining [10]. Unsupervised techniques, including clustering and autoencoders, have been applied when labeled data are scarce, detecting anomalies based on deviations from learned normal behavior. Additionally, physical-layer fingerprinting methods leveraging channel impulse responses, Doppler shifts, and fading profiles have also shown promise for both spoofing protection and jamming detection [8].

Okyere et al. [12] investigated asynchronous Massive MIMO-based PNC resilience under Gaussian barrage jamming. Using sum-difference transformations combined with Maximum A Posteriori (MAP) detection, they demonstrated improved BER performance under varying jamming intensities. However, the resilience of synchronous PNC systems under symbol-level jamming attacks remains insufficiently explored. Motivated by this gap, the present work investigates the impact of SLJ on synchronous PNC-based TWRC systems and proposes an effective detection scheme for secure relay communication under such precise jamming threats.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Subcarrier-Level Signal Model

We consider an OFDM-based TWRC system employing synchronous PNC, as described in [6] and illustrated in Fig. 1. Two users, UE_A and UE_B , exchange data through a relay node R, which faithfully forwards the received signals. A jammer is also present and may disrupt the communication process. Each OFDM symbol contains N active subcarriers. On subcarrier k , the users transmit complex symbols $X_A[k]$ and $X_B[k]$, with frequency-domain channel gains to the relay denoted as $H_{AR}[k]$ and $H_{BR}[k]$, respectively. The received signal at the relay is affected by a symbol-level jamming signal $J[k]$ and additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) $N_R[k]$, modeled as a complex Gaussian random variable $N_R[k] \sim N_C(0, N\sigma_t^2)$, where $\sigma_t^2 = N_0/2$ is the noise variance

per subcarrier, N_0 is the power spectral density of the noise, and N also represents the FFT size used in the system.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the jamming threat in a typical IoT scenario (e.g., a smart factory) employing TWRC communications.

The jammer generates a frequency-domain multicarrier OFDM signal [7], where the jamming symbols occupy specific time-frequency resources with unit magnitude and random phase, while other resource elements remain unjammed. The jammer's OFDM transmitter performs an IFFT operation to place jamming symbols on different subcarriers, producing the time-domain jamming signal as:

$$j[n] = \sum_{k=1}^N J[k] \cdot e^{\frac{2\pi i k n}{N}}, n=0,2,\dots,N-1 \quad (1)$$

where $J[k]$ is the frequency-domain jamming symbol, typically modulated using M-QAM, or M-PSK, and N is the total number of OFDM subcarriers.

In synchronous PNC systems, as discussed in [6], users apply power control and phase alignment (e.g., channel inversion precoding) so that their signals arrive aligned at the relay. Assuming perfect synchronization, the signal received at the relay on the subcarrier k is modeled as:

$$Y_R[k] = X_A[k] + X_B[k] + J[k] \cdot H_{JR}[k] + N_R[k], k=1,2,\dots,N \quad (2)$$

Here, $X_A[k] + X_B[k]$ forms the network-coded composite symbol, $H_{JR}[k]$ denotes the channel gain from the jammer to the relay, and $J[k]$ introduces structured interference from the jammer. The jamming signal $J[k]$ may follow known modulation schemes (e.g., 16-QAM or Gaussian noise) and is time- and frequency-aligned with legitimate OFDM symbols [6], [7].

Jamming attacks targeting the OFDM resource grid can be broadly categorized into three main types: symbol jamming, subcarrier jamming, and random jamming. In symbol jamming, the jammer uniformly interferes with all subcarriers within specific OFDM symbols, with the duty cycle parameter ρ applied per symbol to adjust instantaneous jamming power while maintaining a constant average JSR. In subcarrier jamming, the jammer selectively targets specific subcarriers over time, applying ρ per subcarrier to distribute jamming power over a subset of tones, leaving others unaffected. In random jamming, interference is pulsed randomly across both time and frequency axes, increasing detection complexity due to its unpredictable nature. Across all types, modulation schemes such as 16-QAM and QPSK are employed, with the jamming signal inserted at baseband before the IFFT [7].

In our OFDM-PNC system, the victim signal employs 16-QAM modulation on 48 data subcarriers and 4 pilot subcarriers (at subcarriers 14, 27, 39, and 52), following the IEEE 802.11 frame format [6]. The OFDM symbol also includes 41 guard bands on each spectrum edge, a null at the center subcarrier, and a cyclic prefix length of 16. This work evaluates pilot-assisted SLJ detection schemes in the OFDM-based TWRC system with synchronous PNC, focusing on detection accuracy, precision, and threshold sensitivity under varying JSR, duty cycle, and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) conditions, consistent with the approach in [7].

The average jamming power, measured by the JSR-at the victim receiver, remains constant; however, instantaneous power may increase when employing a pulsed jammer. The duty cycle ρ represents the probability that the jammer is active, with $1-\rho$ being the inactive probability. The instantaneous jamming power is:

$$P_{J,\text{instant}} = \frac{10^{\text{JSRdB}/10}}{\rho} \quad (3)$$

The jammer generates a 16-QAM signal scaled by ρ to assess the effect of different duty cycles at constant SNR and JSR. Assuming the jammer targets all OFDM subcarriers per OFDM symbol, the JSR per OFDM symbol is defined as:

$$\text{JSR}_{\text{Per OFDM symbol}} = \frac{P_{S, \text{ Per OFDM symbol}}}{P_{J, \text{ Per OFDM symbol}}} \quad (4)$$

where P_S , and P_J denote the signal and jamming powers per symbol, respectively.

B. Symbol-Level Jamming Detection in OFDM Systems Using Pilot-Based Thresholding

To detect SLJ, we employ a simulation-based approach to determine the detection threshold, T , at the relay. This threshold is determined based on the received signal model in equation (2). The process of setting this threshold is further elaborated through various jamming detection methods outlined in the following subsections.

1) Energy-based Jamming Detection

In this method, the receiver monitors K known pilot subcarriers per OFDM symbol. Let $X_p[k]$ be the clean pilot symbol and $Y_p[k]$, for $k=1,2,\dots,K$, the received pilot signal. The receiver subtracts the known pilot symbol from the received signal, as shown in equation (2), isolating the jamming and noise residual [8]:

$$\hat{R}[k] = Y_p[k] - 2X_p[k] = J[k].H_{JR}[k] + N_R[k] \quad (5)$$

The detection statistic sums energy across the K pilot subcarriers:

$$E = \sum_{k=1}^K |\hat{R}[k]|^2 \quad (6)$$

Following [8], the detection problem is modeled as a binary hypothesis test. The null hypothesis H_0 indicates no jamming, while the alternative hypothesis H_1 signals symbol-level jamming. The decision rule D is defined as:

$$D = \begin{cases} H_0: E < T & \text{(No jamming present)} \\ H_1: E \geq T & \text{(Symbol-level jamming present)} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where T is a threshold balancing the false alarm probability $P_{FA} = P_r(E \geq T | H_0)$ and detection probability $P_D = P_r(E \geq T | H_1)$ [8]. These probabilities are typically modeled using Chi-square or Gamma distributions based on the pilot subcarriers and noise statistics.

2) EVM-Based Jamming Detection

In modern OFDM and 5G systems, EVM measures the deviation between received IQ symbols and ideal constellation points, providing a sensitive metric for jamming detection.

EVM is computed per symbol using the formula:

$$\text{EVM}_k(\%) = 100 \times \sqrt{\frac{e_k}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (I_k^2 + Q_k^2)}} \quad (8)$$

where $e_k = (I_k - \tilde{I}_k)^2 + (Q_k - \tilde{Q}_k)^2$ represents the squared error between the transmitted reference symbol ($I_k + jQ_k$) and its received version ($\tilde{I}_k + j\tilde{Q}_k$) in the IQ plane. The maximum EVM values across N symbols are then calculated as:

$$\text{EVM}_{\text{MAX}}(\%) = \max_{k=1,2,\dots,N} \text{EVM}_k \quad (9)$$

A threshold test similar to energy detection is applied:

$$\begin{cases} H_0: \text{EVM}_{\text{MAX}} < T & \text{(No jamming present)} \\ H_1: \text{EVM}_{\text{MAX}} \geq T & \text{(Symbol-level jamming present)} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

3) SVM-based Jamming Detection

To improve detection under low SNR and reduce false alarms, ML methods such as Support Vector Machine have been proposed [3], [11].

The SVM-based detector uses EVM-based statistics (EVM_{MAX}) as feature vectors:

$$x_n = [\text{EVM}_{\text{MAX},1}, \text{EVM}_{\text{MAX},2}, \dots, \text{EVM}_{\text{MAX},N}] \quad (11)$$

and is trained on clean (non-jammed) data using a one-class SVM. The detection rule is:

$$D = \begin{cases} H_0: f(x_n) \geq 0 & \text{(No jamming present)} \\ H_1: f(x_n) < 0 & \text{(Symbol-level jamming present)} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $f(x_n)$ is the SVM decision function.

IV. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Simulation Setup

Simulations were conducted on a TWRC system with synchronous PNC, based on the IEEE 802.11 standard using 16-QAM modulation [6]. SLJ was applied, with jamming power controlled by the JSR and duty cycle, ρ . Detection performance was evaluated using energy-based, EVM-based, and one-class SVM-based methods, all implemented in MATLAB. The SVM was trained on 70,000 clean OFDM symbols, while 30,000 clean and 10,000 jammed symbols were reserved for testing. This split ensured robust training and balanced evaluation of false positives and true positives.

B. Threshold Selection for Jamming Detection

Figs. 2 and 3 show the received signal power profiles and threshold calibration for the energy- and EVM-based detection methods across different SNR values. We set the detection thresholds to achieve a target BER of 10^{-4} . For 16-QAM modulation, this threshold corresponds to an SNR of 16 dB in non-jamming conditions, as reported in [6]. We define the Threatening Jamming Power Level (TJPL) as the minimum jamming that causes the BER to exceed this threshold. Figs. 4 and 5 show that as the JSR increases from -20 dB to 15 dB, the EVM and sum-energy metrics rise monotonically with interference power increments. Using Figs. 2 and 3, we set the detection thresholds to approximately 4 and 1 for the energy- and EVM-based methods, respectively.

Fig. 2. Sum energy on the received pilot symbols versus SNR (no jamming) for threshold setting at the PNC system's operating SNR (SNR = 16 dB).

Fig. 3. EVMmax versus SNR (no jamming) for threshold setting at the PNC system's operating SNR (SNR = 16 dB).

Fig. 4. Sum energy on the received pilot symbols for various JSR values at SNR = 16 dB.

Fig. 5. EVMmax for different JSR values at SNR = 16 dB.

C. Performance of Pilot-Assisted and SVM-based Jamming Detection Methods

Figs. 6 and 7 show that, under symbol-level jamming at high JSR levels (JSR ≥ 0 dB, e.g., JSR = 5 dB), the energy-based detection method attains an accuracy of 0.63 and a perfect precision of 1. In comparison, the EVM-based detection method achieves flawless performance with both accuracy and precision equal to 1. This ensures reliable detection at high JSR levels, even under conditions where the BER is low and throughput remains unaffected. Conversely, at low JSR levels (JSR < 0 dB, e.g., JSR = -5 dB), the SVM-based detector achieves the highest performance, achieving an accuracy of 0.99 and a precision of 0.97. By modeling the statistical distribution of clean symbols, the SVM can detect subtle anomalies caused by jamming signals, enabling it to consistently outperform other detection methods. This performance advantage is particularly notable at low JSR levels, where the impact of jamming is less pronounced and more challenging to identify.

Fig. 6. Accuracy for different values of JSR, and the fixed values of SNR=16dB, and $\rho=0.25$.

Fig. 7. Precision for different values of JSR, and the fixed values of SNR=16dB, and $\rho=0.25$.

We evaluated detection performance across ρ values ranging from 0.1 to 0.9 under low JSR conditions (e.g., JSR=-5 dB). Figs. 8 and 9 show that, for $\rho < 0.2$, the accuracy of the energy-based method drops from 42% to 28%, while the EVM- and SVM-based methods maintain accuracy above 90%. Although energy-based detection provides slightly higher precision for $\rho < 0.45$, SVM still maintains precision above 91% even at low ρ . Overall, SVM achieves the best combined accuracy and precision for $\rho \geq 0.45$ and consistently outperforms the other methods across all ρ values. Minor discrepancies, such as the slight drop in EVM accuracy at higher ρ , stem from threshold selection errors.

Fig. 8. Accuracy for different values of ρ and the fixed values of SNR=16dB, and JSR=-5 dB.

Fig. 9. Precision for different values of ρ and the fixed values of SNR=16dB, and JSR=-5 dB.

D. Metric Prioritization in Jamming Detection Applications

The choice of performance metric in jamming detection depends on the specific application scenario. For jammer localization, precision is important because only jammed nodes are relevant. High precision minimizes false positives, preventing unnecessary resource allocation to unaffected nodes. In contrast, in rerouting scenarios, accuracy is more critical since both jammed and non-jammed nodes influence network operation [13]. High accuracy ensures minimal misclassification, supporting optimal routing decisions and maintaining overall network performance.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates pilot-assisted SLJ detection in an OFDM-based TWRC system with synchronous PNC,

focusing on detection accuracy and precision under varying JSR, duty cycle, and SNR conditions. Results show that ML, particularly SVM-based detection, significantly improves system resilience to SLJ. While energy-based detection is simple and effective against strong jamming, it lacks sensitivity to weak interference. EVM-based detection offers improved robustness by tracking constellation distortions, whereas SVM-based detection achieves the highest accuracy without requiring threshold tuning. These findings underscore the potential of ML-based approaches for robust jamming mitigation in modern wireless relay networks.

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